

THE IMPACT OF USING ICT ON LEARNING ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION: This article briefly describes the development of English language classes with more and more information technology, and more work with students.

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With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which is one of the peculiarities of our time, special attention is paid to a new approach to the educational process and its organization, using its potential.

The role of the teacher in the classroom is also changing. The teacher is now mainly a facilitator. It is time for teachers who want to keep pace with the times to be ready to bring any part of the lesson to life through ICT.

Indeed, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, the targeted organization of lessons in the form of games that interest students is very large. It is becoming an integral part of the learning process. In order to teach English to young people through computers, first of all, the teacher must be able to use computer technology at a professional level. This level of use includes not only the full use of the existing capabilities of the computer, but also the ability to create new training programs based on it. To become a teacher at this level, every foreign language teacher needs to work harder on himself in the field of modern technology. There are several advantages to teaching English over a computer using traditional methods of teaching. 'winter) will be an opportunity to test their skills. This is now possible with the help of advanced software. Only in this way can the student be properly directed.

In addition, every rule, every word, every unit of understanding taught in a foreign language with the help of a computer is better stored in the memory of the student. Naturally, the rich graphic capabilities of the computer, the ability to convey information about the situation in audio, text, image and video form make it one of the most effective ways to teach a foreign language through a computer. In general, it is better to use Word and Power Point to explain current issues. Because I think it's much easier for students to understand when they

cover a topic using spreadsheets using Word. Power Point can be used to engage students in audio, visual, and video presentations.

We are increasingly confronted with the fact that knowing a foreign language (currently the most popular language is English) is becoming a vital necessity. Joining world culture, communicating with almost any foreign representative, a great opportunity to study abroad - knowing English (and other foreign languages) opens the door to the world and helps you find a suitable job, which is a plus in both. reading and in daily life.

There are different options for using ICT, but there are three main ones:

lecture courses, practical and laboratory classes, distance learning.

In the classroom, the teacher can use:

- Presentations created by teachers and students or presentations from the Internet.
- Electronic encyclopedias. (For example, "Encyclopedia of Cyril and Myth")
- Electronic textbooks. (The student is first invited to view the course or conduct a virtual experiment based on the knowledge gained, and then go through a software knowledge control system).
- Interactive trainings (for example, to prepare for an exam).
- Test constructors that allow the teacher to formulate the questions of the assignments and enter the grade set by the computer in the journal.

The main types of lessons according to the method of using information technology:

- Lessons using a computer projector in demo mode or an interactive whiteboard.
- Individual computer lessons - lessons are taught in a computer class that does not have access or is connected to the Internet.

Using an interactive whiteboard will make the lesson more efficient, the dynamism of the lesson will increase, video animation and video interaction will be possible, for example, the ability to quickly retrieve data from automated automakers 'websites via the Internet. In other words, the teacher can always be in the information field of any field, with minimal effort on his part. Another advantage of the interactive whiteboard is the ability to communicate wirelessly with the computer, thanks to the Bluetooth function, the data entered using the interactive whiteboard is stored in the computer's memory. Interactive tablets can perform the same functions. Video conferencing using an interactive whiteboard allows participants to exchange data entered from different computers in real time, no matter where they are.

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